

SOCIOLINGUISTIC PROFILE OF FOREIGN PHILOLOGY LEARNERS

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Abstract: This research paper introduces the selected group of foreign philology faculty first-year students from the perspective of sociolinguistics. Regarding the analysis of learners' sociolinguistic profile, we have figured it out from the point of identity, race, ethnicity, geography language, and disability. “Generally, ELT must be placed within a larger macro-societal framework, recognizing that language pedagogy has been isolated from the social sciences for too long. This broader perspective is crucial to understanding how language learning is shaped by social, political, and economic factors” (Philipson, 1992, p.2).

This research culminates practical recommendations for all philology students with different backgrounds by addressing students' individual needs in subgroups. These strategies can ensure that teaching effectively considers diverse linguistic backgrounds and learning styles.

Keywords: Subgroup, multilingualism, race, ethnicity, gender, sexuality, pedagogical implications, assessment implications.

Sociolinguistic Profile of a group of learners. For this sociolinguistic profile, group XT-2420 has been chosen, In total, there are 14 students, 3 of them male and 11 female. Students are the very first year Bachelor’s degree students in the foreign philology faculty and the average age from 17 to 19 among them. Most of the learners are Uzbeks and their first language is Uzbek, a few students speak Persian as a primary language. Moreover, students are multilingual they are fluent in Uzbek, Russian, and Persian. Approximately 60% of the students are Uzbek. They independently and consciously learned the target language until their bachelor's degree (BA) and the course which is conducted in the spring semester is the language aspects of the English language. Their current level is B2 (Vantage) on the CEFR scale, which indicates fluency sufficient for spontaneous interaction with native speakers. Their IELTS score is likely between 6 and 6.5. Their target level is C1 (Advanced). The course of the aspects of the English language covers all integrated skills and grammatical features. These students began developing their skills through theory- and practice-based (seminars) lessons. Their language proficiency has improved steadily through various teaching methods like Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), the Audio-lingual Method, and Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL). They actively participate in class and readily tackle challenging assignments.

While highly motivated (both intrinsically and extrinsically) and cooperative learners, they sometimes struggle with maintaining consistent participation during seminars due to occasional lapses in motivation. Additionally, their speech can lack clarity and fluency. When writing essays, they face difficulty supporting their arguments effectively within paragraphs. Pronunciation errors are noticeable while pronouncing the words. The fossilization can also be noticed in their speech, affecting their fluency.

These students actively strive to achieve their learning goals despite their challenges in classes. Their classes (80 minutes each, 2 times a week) with content-based and skill-based syllabuses, along with course materials like Navigate and skills-focused books by Cambridge University Press such as Vocabulary in Use for upper-intermediate.

When it comes to the subgroups, they differ from each other

1. This subgroup contains students who come from different suburban parts of Uzbekistan and they are the natives of the Uzbek language where the Uzbek language is dominant in their life such as family, friends and so on. (geography)
2. The second subgroup has 3 learners born in Uzbekistan and they may be more proficient in their home language (Persian) rather than Uzbek depending on family preferences and practices. (Language and ethnicity)
3. The subgroup has only one learner who has a visual impairment (blind) and lives in a city and her dominant language is Uzbek where she communicates with this language everywhere. (Disability)

As can be seen, the subgroups are different in the points of language, ethnicity and disability. These students have a high rate of difficulty while learning. Most of the time they need a peer to help and care in class. Taylor (2016) noted that Non-essential graphics should be eliminated or replaced with clear textual descriptions. Furthermore, the difference between texts and the speed should be taken into consideration by stakeholders. These descriptions must avoid language that sighted test-takers would readily generate without prompting. Recent studies in sociolinguistics have demonstrated the remarkable ability of language practices to define and even change ethnicity. According to Buchholtz (as cited in Fought, 2011) "The ideological connection between ethnicity and language is so powerful that adopting language habits specific to a certain ethnic group may be enough to pass for a member of that group.

Sociolinguistic profile of the learning context. Worlds Language University (UZSWLU) provides a structured atmosphere for students to acquire the hard skills to become EFL teachers. University is more welcome to accept all people whether it's religion, gender, ethnicity or social status. The teaching curriculum provided by stakeholders and assessment is based on the standard CEFR framework. All sources

whether it is e-version or hard copy all is available for students. Instruction focuses on developing foundational grammar, vocabulary, reading comprehension, and writing skills however according to the specification of each group (philology, literacy, translation) they have special theoretical and practical lectures and seminars as well. The course which is considered in this formative assessment is Language Aspects conducted twice a week for 80 minutes.

From the point of linguistic profiling, the educational establishment considers cultural diversity which aligns the students with each other. "In contrast to "linguistic profiling," which is based on aural clues that may include racial identification, "racial profiling" is based on visual cues that lead to the confirmation or speculation of the racial heritage of an individual or identification, but it can also be utilised to recognise other linguistic subgroups that exist within a specific speech community" (Baugh,2015, p.4).

From the point of Gender & sexuality – there are no restrictions on having conversations about gender and sexuality while creating a good inclusive atmosphere which respects every orientation is very crucial. Each learners have their rights and all preferences are respected by authorities and students unless it does not impact the quality of learning and teaching system.

Race & Ethnicity - in UZSWLU conversing about race and ethnicity can be beneficial to explore cultural diversity, and identities and also to grasp students' knowledge. It is very important to consider being noticed and sensitive while speaking about various inappropriate assumptions, and stereotypes which create discomfort about others. Lippi-Green (1997) mentioned that ethnic stereotypes can change social attitudes considerably. It is clear that the relevance of this is the way all aspects are demonstrated through the systematic construction of dominance and subordinate in animated films aimed at children.

Pedagogical implications. This part introduces different pedagogical implications which are provided during the class on the Aspects of the English Language.

Here are the samples of implications:

- Considering methods for multilingual learners, fluency in English is likely a common goal. However, a concern arises when students with languages like Persian might face pronunciation challenges due to differing sound systems.

- I am thinking about grouping from the point of view of students with different backgrounds. Regarding dividing into groups from the point of view of multilingual students. A concern I have about this view is that dividing them based on their ethnicity will cause discrimination.

-I consider methods from the point of view of different-level students. The differentiation technique from the point of view of low-level students might struggle in-class activities to participate.

- Inappropriate topics which might insult disabled students in seminars lead to disrespect for the learners. (such as a story of a blind girl) Choosing a proper, common context where students can feel good in the classroom creates a good learning atmosphere.

These pedagogical implications emphasize treating students equitably. This means ensuring all students receive the support they need to succeed, regardless of factors like visual impairment, deafness, or nationality. Bayley & Villarreal (2018) considered students use languages for a variety of purposes. Notably, immigrant students in inner-circle countries are more likely to interact with speakers of vernacular dialects than with speakers of the most standardized varieties. The more we, as teachers, understand the linguistic ecology of the worlds our students inhabit, the better equipped we will be to help them acquire the different registers they need to achieve their personal goals.

While equal treatment is important, recognizing individual needs is crucial for effective learning. For instance, in this research, there is only one disabled student who reads braille, except others she cannot handle everything. Differentiation instruction might provide an effective rise of engagement and positiveness among students. Tomlinson (2001) considered the best differentiation strategies are planned in advance by teachers. This proactive approach ensures lessons are designed to address diverse learning styles and needs, unlike a one-size-fits-all approach that requires scrambling to adjust plans when it becomes clear some students are struggling.

Assessment implications. Using a range of assessment types such as project work, performance-based (role-play), presentations or classroom participation will provide better understanding and development of students. Moreover, shortening repetition, and drills and focusing on students' performance on cultural background and the language itself is helpful because students might use it in real-life situations. Also, need to avoid culturally biased questions and tasks where students feel stressed or inappropriate in class while doing it.

Mainly to assess students fairly, the following criteria provide fairness of the assessments:

- Consider the assessment catering to different learner styles: kinesthetic, auditory, and visual.

- To reduce anxiety by providing definitions in both English, Uzbek and Persian language for students.

- Using braille, or screen readers and enlarged printed materials for students who are studying with difficulty (visual impairment).

- Modifying standard alternative assessments which are available for disabled students.

Taylor & Chen (2016) For written constructed responses, braille-reading test-takers can dictate their essays or short answers to a scribe. They may spell out content words and indicate punctuation if these elements are part of the scoring criteria. The scribe can then read back the text for editing. Alternatively, test-takers can type their responses using a keyboard or braille writer.

For paired speaking tasks, if the prompt is provided in writing, it can be presented in braille for the visually impaired test-taker and in print for their sighted partner (whose performance is not being assessed) at an appropriate proficiency level. Additional time would be allocated to accommodate the time needed to read the braille prompt” (p.13)

Conclusion

Generally, this research paper identifies the philology undergraduate students who are acquiring their hard skills at University. From the point of sociolinguistics, their group tested and learned based on the sociolinguistic-specific contextual factors. The group of students are multilingual and different from each other. Deumert (2011) outlined that “Multilingualism is often seen by linguists as a gradient phenomenon, with an emphasis on the extremes of this continuum: those who are fully proficient in several languages compared to people whose knowledge is restricted to a few simple phrases” (p.4).

Fleming (2019) outlined the role of ideology and scale (national & local) in shaping languages in Kazakhstan (which is as close to the Uzbek language as the Turkic language), he uses the sociolinguistic framework of language and ideology. The relevance of this source is that the ideology, multilingualism and language policy cover the whole research which helps to know more about them.

Mainly both pedagogical and assessment implications are focused on each subgroup that might require specific considerations. These implications can corporate activities which promote awareness of sociolinguistic factors, cultural norms, and appropriate language use for students before conducting the lessons. The assessment implication is to show justice in exams where teachers can fairly assess students, and provide teachers with insights into student understanding., they can see what students are grasping and when and where they need support. Implications require students to justify their language choices in different contexts. “A promising approach to developing sociocultural competence (SC) in the language classroom is embedding explicit teaching of sociolinguistics during instruction. By raising learners' conscious awareness of key sociolinguistic concepts, teachers can help their students both recognize and produce systematic variations of language forms according to their

varying appropriateness across different contexts and conditions of use” (Booven, 2018, p.3-4).

To conclude, I recommend contributing more coursebooks and textbooks written in English-Uzbek-Russian or Persian for learners and their mentors to inspire them and help them engage in the seminars actively. Moreover, hiring teachers who can speak Persian and Russian will improve the learning atmosphere. Organising special courses that require translanguaging techniques for those who want to improve their English for the beginner stage allows them to know more deeply.

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